

A NOTE ON THE ANALYSIS OF CERTAIN ALGÆ.

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Though some work on drift sea-weed collected from the various places along the coast line of the Bombay Presidency was done (Dixit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **12**, 959), no work seems to have been made hitherto on the drift sea-weeds collected along the Coromandal coast. The authors collected four species of sea-weeds from different places in the Madras Presidency during the winter months of 1930. The result of analysis of air-dried samples is tabulated below.

Weed.	Cellulose.	Protein.	Iodine.	Place.
Padina	18.7 %	15.2 %	Nil	Bhimilipatam (Vizagapatam District).
Ulva	31.0	1.0	Nil	Vizagapatam.
Enteromorpha	24.4	2.6	Nil	Vizagapatam.
Red algae (Poly-siphonia)	18	7.75	0.044 %	Pamban (Ramnad District).

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